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БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

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OTITIS MEDIA WITH EFFUSION IN CHILDREN: A REVIEW

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ANNOTATION

Pediatric otitis media with effusion, or OME, is a common condition. The illness is frequently asymptomatic, making it simple to overlook. On the other hand, OME may result in hearing loss that hinders the child's behavioral and linguistic development. The diagnosis is primarily clinical, derived via otoscopy and, in certain situations, tympanometry. Only when obstructive adenoid hypertrophy is suspected or when there is a case of unilateral OME is nasal endoscopy recommended. When middle ear effusion is noted at consultations spaced three months apart, the condition is known as otitis media with effusion. In order to avoid overlooking any further underlying causes of deafness (such as perception deafness), hearing must be assessed both before and after treatment (using an age-appropriate audiometry approach). The development of OME is favoured by craniofacial dysmorphism, respiratory allergies, and gastro-oesophageal reflux.

Key words: Otitis media with effusion, Tympanostomy tube, Ventilation tube, Grommet, Child

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СРЕДНИЙ ОТИТ С ВЫПОТОМ У ДЕТЕЙ: ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫЙ ОБЗОР**АННОТАЦИЯ**

Детский средний отит с выпотом, или СОВ, является распространенным заболеванием. Заболевание часто протекает бессимптомно, поэтому его легко не заметить. СОВ может привести к потере слуха, что препятствует языковому развитию ребенка. Клинический диагноз в первую очередь, устанавливается с помощью отоскопии и в некоторых ситуациях, тимпанометрии. Назальная эндоскопия рекомендуется только при подозрении на обструктивную гипертрофию аденоидов или при одностороннем СОВ. Когда на консультациях с интервалом в три месяца отмечается выпот в среднем ухе, это состояние называется средним отитом с выпотом. Чтобы не упустить из виду какие-либо дополнительные причины глухоты (например, восприятия), слух необходимо оценивать как до, так и после лечения (с использованием аудиометрического подхода, соответствующего возрасту). Развитию СОВ благоприятствуют черепно-лицевой дисморфизм, респираторная аллергия и гастроэзофагеальный рефлюкс.

Ключевые слова: Средний отит с выпотом, Тимпаностомическая трубка, Вентиляционная трубка, Ребенок

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BOLALARDA EKSUDATIV O'RTA OTIT: ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI**ANNOTATSIYA**

Eksudativ o'rta otit (EO`O) bolalarda keng tarqalgan kassalikdir. Kasallik ko'pincha asemptomatik tarzda kechadi, shuning uchun uni o'tkazib yuborish juda ham oson. EO`O eshitish qobiliyatini yo'qotishiga olib kelishi mumkin, bu esa bolaning xatti-harakati va nutq rivojlanishiga to'sqinlik qiladi. Klinik tashxis asosan, otoskopiya va ba'zi hollarda timpanometriyadan foydalanadi. Burun endoskopiyasi faqat obstruktiv adenoid gipertrofiyasi yoki bir tomonlama (EO`O) bilan shubha qilingan hollarda tavsifiya etiladi. O'rta quloqning oqishi har uch oy oraliqda qayd etilganda, bu holat eksudativ o'rta otit deb ataladi. Karlikning qo'shimcha sabablarini (masalan, idrok etish) e'tibordan chetda qoldirmaslik uchun eshitishni davolashdan oldin ham, keyin ham baholash kerak (yoshga mos audiometrik yondashuvdan foydalangan holda). EO`O kraniofatsiyal dismorfizm, nafas olish allergiyasi va gastroezofagial refluyuks rivojlanishiga olib keladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Effuziya bilan to'lgan o'rta otit, Timpanostomiya trubkasi, Ventilyatsiya trubkasi, Bola

INTRODUCTION

Mawson originally defined otitis media with effusion (OME), often referred to as sero-mucous otitis media, in 1976 as the condition where there is fluid in the middle ear chambers but no signs of an acute infection. This kind of chronic otitis media does not result in a perforation of the tympanic membrane. Because of localized inflammation that results in epithelial metaplasia, liquid accumulates in the middle ear chambers. The middle ear effusion is not purulent; rather, it is either mucous or sero-mucous. The condition lasts for at least three months, in contrast to persistent effusion that follows acute medium otitis, which disappears in 90% of cases within two months (Blanc et al., 2018).

Even young infants can be impacted by OME; in fact, 50% of instances, according to Casselbrant and Mandel (2003), sixty percent of cases include infants under the age of two, and fifty percent involve newborns under the age of one. The prevalence is notably high (between 60 and 85%) in children with craniofacial anomalies, particularly trisomy 21 and cleft palate, according to Flynn et al. (2009) and Maris et al. (2014). Persistent OME can lead to hearing loss and tympanic membrane degradation (atrophy, retraction pockets, and cholesteatoma), according to Maw et al. (1999). It may also delay language acquisition and result in aberrant behaviors (Aarhus et al., 2015).

Risk factors

Medical and non-medical risk factors can be used to categorize OME risk factors. Age (two to five years old), a large family, a sibling's history of OME, the brief period of breastfeeding, and passive smoking are significant non-medical risk factors. Acute tonsillitis, nasal blockage, craniofacial abnormalities, and a history of acute otitis media (AOM) are important medical risk factors.

1. Assessment of OME in children

The goals of clinical evaluation and supplemental research are to ascertain whether OME is straightforward or complex, whether simple follow-up or treatment is required, and whether OME is isolated or linked to other conditions that could need special attention.

1.1. Clinical examination

The existence of an effusion behind the tympanic membrane that has lasted longer than three months is the basis for the diagnosis of OME. Tympanometry in conjunction with otoscopy, suggestive kinds of otoscopy, or even pneumatic otoscopy (grade A) might be used to demonstrate this effusion.

A crucial component in evaluating OME is nasal endoscopy:

- in the event of a grade C unilateral OME;
- in the event that the youngster breathes through their mouth or snores (grade C);
- when adenoidectomy is planned without the need to implant a tympanostomy tube (professional consensus).

1.2. Complementary investigations

The sole requirement is hearing evaluation, which needs to be carried out methodically [12].

It is advised to use pure tone and speech audiometry, preferably with free-field testing, for diagnosing OME in children who have balance issues, learning disabilities, or language delays. (A+).

According to professional opinion, subjective audiometric testing or, in the event that subjective audiometry is not possible, objective intraoperative audiometric testing must systematically precede the installation of tympanostomy tubes.

In children with language delay, learning difficulties, balance disorders, or high audiometric thresholds prior to treatment (grade A), an audiometric examination must be conducted following OME treatment to verify the absence of sensorineural hearing loss or conductive hearing loss of ossicular origin.

In situations where audiometric testing cannot be done with headphones and there are extremely high free-field thresholds (grade A), auditory evoked potentials (AEP) or auditory steady-state responses (ASSR) are advised either during the tympanostomy tube implantation process or following OME resolution [13].

For the diagnosis of OME and the treatment of simple types (grade B), imaging is ineffective.

1.3. Assessment of gastro-oesophageal reflux disorder (GERD)

According to professional consensus, screening for GERD is warranted if there are symptoms suggestive of GERD (grade A), if OME is severe and occurs beyond the age of seven, or if OME is linked to other conditions like recurrent rhinosinusitis (grade C) or laryngitis [15].

2. Diagnosis

When OME is suspected, otoscopy should be done. It is best to use pneumatic otoscopy, which ought to be broadly accessible. The following table shows how OME differs from other prevalent middle ear illnesses in terms of clinical characteristics and otoscopic findings.

3. Efficacy of tympanostomy tubes in the control of hearing loss and its consequences

One possible cause of mild to severe conductive hearing loss is otitis media with effusion. Hearing levels between 10 and 40 dB may be found in up to 60% of children with OME [16].

When inserted properly and kept patent (grade A), tympanostomy tubes can restore normal hearing [17], [18]. However, once they fall out or are removed (grade A), they have no effect on the long-term auditory threshold [17].

4. Efficacy of tympanostomy tubes in the control of recurrent OME

In children under three years old (grade A), tympanostomy tubes can lower the frequency of OME episodes [19], [20], [21], [22], [23].

5. Efficacy of tympanostomy tubes in the prevention of tympanic membrane atrophy and its consequences

Following the implantation of a tympanostomy tube, the incidence of spontaneous mild OME sequelae, such as myringosclerosis (10%) and tympanic membrane atrophy (14%), increases [24], [25]. Tympanostomy tube-related myringosclerosis is confined to the tympanic membrane and never affects the middle ear. In the same way, tympanic membrane atrophy hardly ever develops into a cholesteatoma or significant retraction pocket. Tympanostomy tubes, however, stop cholesteatoma from growing [26], [27].

6. Efficacy of tympanostomy tubes in the prevention of recurrent OME

After they are removed (grade A) or fall out, tympanostomy tubes stop OME from happening again [28], [29]. In children older than four years old (grade A), associated adenoidectomy amplifies the positive benefits of tympanostomy tubes on OME [30], [31], [32]. Therefore, it seems sense to save adenoidectomy for kids younger than 4 years old who have obstructive and/or nasopharyngeal infectious issues.

7. Efficacy of adenoidectomy and other surgical procedures in the control of OME

7.1. Adenoidectomy

When compared to children who are not treated by adenoidectomy, children over 4 years old who receive standard adenoidectomy (curettage) and tympanostomy tube implantation had a much reduced OME recurrence rate and significantly fewer tube placements. Children under the age of four do not show any discernible differences [29], [41], [42], [43], [44]. Adenoidectomy should only be done in children under 4 years old in cases of symptomatic adenoid hypertrophy (nasal obstruction, recurrent infections) due to the risk of bleeding [29].

In comparison to curettage adenoidectomy (grade A), endoscopic microdebrider adenoidectomy seems to be safer and at least as effective on OME [45], [46], [47], and [48]. However, this technique has not yet been the subject of a health economics evaluation.

7.2. Myringotomy

While myringotomy and adenoidectomy have been demonstrated to be effective in the treatment of OME (grade A), the 6-month quality of life after tympanostomy tube implantation appears to be superior [49], [50], and [51]. Professional consensus states that in the context of managing OME, radiofrequency or laser myringotomy, as well as the administration of mitomycin C during myringotomy, are not indicated in the absence of proven data.

7.3. Mastoid antrum ventilator tube

Professional consensus states that mastoid antrum ventilator tube implantation is not advised in the treatment of OME in children in the absence of evidence.

8. Efficacy of medical treatments in the control of OME

Oral antibiotic therapy does not enhance medium- or long-term hearing and has minimal effect on the retrotympenic effusion [52]. It does not qualify as a reference treatment for OME (grade A) since it carries a risk of side effects and the emergence of bacterial resistance.

It has not been demonstrated that antihistamines or decongestants are helpful in the medium- or long-term resolution of retrotympenic effusion [53], [54].

It is not considered a standard treatment for OME because oral or nasal corticosteroid therapy does not improve medium- or long-term hearing or the clearance of the retrotympenic effusion [55]. Topical or oral corticosteroid therapy has the potential to be temporarily successful (grade A) [56].

Mucolytics have been shown to increase OME in one-third of children, but their long-term effectiveness is unknown (grade B).

9. Efficacy of pressure treatments and thermal therapy in the control of OME

In order to treat otitis media with effusion (OME) in children and adults, numerous local treatments have been suggested; however, there has been little research done to assess their effectiveness, and opinions on the matter are divided. Practitioners have different protocols that include local therapies, and there are no explicit guidelines supporting or opposing the use of these methods.

In cooperative children over 4 years old, self-insufflation or balloon tubal insufflation (e.g., Otovent) techniques can be used to address inflammatory otitis with effusion (grade B) (no specific information regarding OME).

We were unable to locate any recent research on the use of conventional aerosol therapy for OME in the literature we reviewed.

In order to establish aerosol therapy protocols (such as the number of sessions and treatment duration) and recommended molecules, randomized controlled trials would be required to validate the role of aerosol therapy in the management of OME.

When combined with thermal therapy, sulfurous water insufflations can help with OME's side effects (tympanometry, hearing) [61], [62], but they haven't been shown to be effective in curing grade C OME in children. However, thermal therapy cannot be advised as a first-line treatment (grade C) in the lack of evaluations of the health economics, quality of life, and long-term efficacy of these therapies.

CONCLUSION

A common pathology in children is otitis media with effusion, which can develop into cholesteatomatous chronic otitis if the condition is not closely watched. Using an otoscopy, the diagnosis can be made rather quickly during a consultation. It is necessary to assess hearing loss both before and after treatment. Pharmacological treatments may be helpful in treating symptoms in the short term, but they cannot be recommended for the treatment of OME due to their lack of long-term effectiveness (especially with relation to the auditory threshold), related unpleasant events, and expense. The only procedure that has received worldwide scientific validation is the insertion of a tympanostomy tube. These devices have demonstrated effectiveness in raising the auditory threshold, stopping OME from recurring, and halting the development of middle ear cholesteatoma. When OME is exacerbated by transmission deafness or structural changes to the tympanic membrane, such as retractions, tympanostomy tubes are recommended. If nasal endoscopy reveals hypertrophy in children older than 4 years old, adenoidectomy and TT placement may be combined; in younger children, TT implantation may be necessary if nasal blockage or recurrent rhinopharyngeal infections are present. To ensure that any issues are not overlooked, the youngsters need to be monitored for a number of years. Youngsters who could have learning or language impairments need to be regularly watched.

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